

Environmental Science and Pollution Research

Application of *Sporosarcina pasteurii* for the biomineralization of calcite in the treatment of waste concrete fines

--Manuscript Draft--

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Abstract:	<p>In this study, we explored and described various parameters of microbially induced calcite precipitation (MICP) using the alkaliphilic bacterium <i>Sporosarcina pasteurii</i> DSM 33, which exhibits ureolytic activity, to stabilize and strengthen waste concrete fines (WCF). Bacterial cell concentration, single and repeated addition of bacterial suspension, and pH adjustment were tested in stage 1 of the experimental agenda in order to tune parameters for sample preparation in stage 2 focused on the effect of MICP treatment duration (14, 30, 60, and 90 days). Two types of WCF materials differing in their physicochemical properties were used for the stabilization. The results of the EDS and XRD analyses confirmed the presence of CaCO₃ crystals, which increased by about 10-12% over time, affecting the porosity, compactness, and strength of the formed composites. The XRD results also indicated that the WCF properties significantly influence the formation of the type of CaCO₃ crystals, supported also by microscopy observations. This study highlights the potential of MICP technology to make concrete recycling more sustainable, aligning with the concept of a circular economy; however, the interplay between the WCF materials of various properties and bacterial activity must be further scrutinized.</p>	
Response to Reviewers:	<p>Dear reviewers and editor, Thank you very much for all the suggestions, which helped us to improve our manuscript. We have revised the manuscript according to all your recommendations. The comments are listed below, and revised manuscripts with and without marked changes are enclosed. All co-authors agree with these changes. We hope that you will find our new version acceptable for publication. Thank you very much for another</p>	

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Sincerely,
Kristyna Klikova, Hana Stiborova

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Thank you for your insightful comment. We have revised the 'Introduction' to provide a more comprehensive comparison with state-of-the-art research, highlighting the significance of our study in the context of related research areas, including bio-inspired heavy metal fixation methods and enzyme-induced carbonate precipitation (EICP) technology. Additionally, we have incorporated new references to strengthen the background and guide general readers through recent advancements in bio-inspired material stabilization.

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We appreciate your questions regarding the purpose and applicability of this study. The primary purpose of our work is to explore the potential of microbially induced calcite precipitation (MICP) as a treatment for waste concrete fines (WCF), specifically focusing on its feasibility as a sustainable method for recycling. This study is rooted in fundamental research aimed at assessing the initial effectiveness of MICP technology in stabilizing WCF, a process still evolving and requiring further development before large-scale application.

Regarding the "no evident advantage" concern, this research establishes foundational knowledge that could inform future advancements, which may address practical applications, cost considerations, and scale-up potential. While our study did not encompass the economic analysis, future research can build on these findings to explore the cost-effectiveness of MICP for concrete recycling. Additionally, as suggested, we included a brief discussion of the potential for chemical interaction between the treated WCF and cement in new concrete formulations, as this warrants more in-depth investigation.

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We acknowledge that the physicochemical properties of waste concrete fines (WCF) play a crucial role in calcium carbonate crystal precipitation and could influence the final properties of the composite samples. While our current study focused on demonstrating the feasibility of MICP as a treatment for WCF, we recognize the importance of investigating factors such as grading size distribution after treatment, dissolution under varying pH conditions, and quantifying crushability. These aspects are discussed in further detail in our related work Holeček et al. (2024), where we specifically examine the effects of these physicochemical parameters on MICP-treated materials. Future studies could expand on this to better quantify their influence on composite performance.

Materials and methods: Please explain how the grading size distribution of the fines was measured. Please detail the saline solution used to suspend the bacteria during cultivation.

The grading size distribution of the fines was measured using laser diffraction, providing precise particle size analysis. Additionally, the saline solution used to suspend the bacteria during cultivation consisted of 9 g/L of sodium chloride (NaCl) in distilled water, sterilized by autoclaving at 121 °C for 15 minutes. This information has been added to the 'Materials and Methods' section for clarity (lines 167-168).

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Indeed, some cases are in which the treatment was longer than 10 days, but adding only calcifying solution after the first 3 days.

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Additional Information:	
Question	Response
§Are you submitting to a Special Issue?	Yes
(If "yes") Please select a Special Issue from the following list: as follow-up to "§Are you submitting to a Special Issue?" "	SI: CHANIA 2023

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Thank you for your comment. We have addressed this by adding quantitative measurements of compactness and strength, including indentation testing with graphical data to provide objective, instrument-based evaluation. These additions strengthen our analysis by offering precise, reproducible measurements of the treated samples' mechanical properties.

The cracks of the final aggregates shown in Figure 3 appear to be caused by drying. This is a

behaviour of fine materials in general. It would be relevant the authors to search for papers in which biocementation was applied to clayey soils and not sands, for comparison.

We agree that drying-induced cracking is a common behavior in fine materials, as seen in biocemented clays. However, in our study, we observed that only certain samples exhibited cracking, likely due to their relatively weak and brittle structure. Given the free-shrinkage conditions and small specimen sizes, the cracking occurred predominantly in these weaker samples, suggesting a correlation between material brittleness and crack formation.

In my opinion the change from vaterite (soluble) into calcite (insoluble, so durable) during "curing" is the most relevant aspect to discuss and explore in the future. Biocementation has more similarity with lime treatment than with cement treatment, so we need the help of specialists with deep knowledge on chemistry such as the authors of this paper to help us to improve this treatment so it will be more feasible for real applications.

Thank you for your comment. Yes, vaterite transforms to calcite (in Portland cement concrete). The transformation is driven by the thermodynamic preference for the more stable calcite form. The primary mechanism is dissolution of vaterite followed by reprecipitation of calcite, facilitated by moisture and CO₂ in the environment. We have observed differences in calcite formations if curing was 14 days or 90 days. You are right, but the results show that there is not always more calcite formation after the experiment is over (a difference of 14 and 90 days is observed for the highway samples, not for the gutter samples).

References:

Holeček, P., Nežerka, V., Kliková, K., & Stiborová, H. (2024). Exploring Porosity's Role in Stiffening Waste Concrete Conglomerates Synthesized with Microbial Calcite: A Micromechanical Analysis. *Waste and Biomass Valorization*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12649-024-02486-4>

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Application of *Sporosarcina pasteurii* for the biomineralization of calcite in the treatment of waste concrete fines

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ABSTRACT

In this study, we explored and described various parameters of microbially induced calcite precipitation (MICP) using the alkaliphilic bacterium *Sporosarcina pasteurii* DSM 33, which exhibits ureolytic activity, to stabilize and strengthen waste concrete fines (WCF). Bacterial cell concentration, single and repeated addition of bacterial suspension, and pH adjustment were tested in stage 1 of the experimental agenda in order to tune parameters for sample preparation in stage 2 focused on the effect of MICP treatment duration (14, 30, 60, and 90 days). Two types of WCF materials differing in their physicochemical properties were used for the stabilization. The results of the EDS and XRD analyses confirmed the presence of CaCO₃ crystals, which increased by about 10-12% over time, affecting the porosity, compactness, and strength of the formed composites. The XRD results also indicated that the WCF properties significantly influence the formation of the type of CaCO₃ crystals, supported also by microscopy observations. This study highlights the potential of MICP technology to make concrete recycling more sustainable, aligning with the concept of a circular economy; however, the interplay between the WCF materials of various properties and bacterial activity must be further scrutinized.

Keywords: MICP, *Sporosarcina pasteurii*, ureolytic activity, CaCO₃ crystals, waste concrete fines

ABBREVIATIONS

BSE	Backscattered electron
EDS	Energy-dispersive spectrometry
MICP	Microbially induced calcite precipitation
NB	Nutrient broth
OD	Optical density
PTFE	Polytetrafluorethylene
RCA	Recycled concrete aggregate
SEM	Scanning electron microscopy
TSA	Trypton soya agar
TSB	Trypton soya broth
WCF	Waste concrete fines
WCF-H	Waste concrete fines – highway
WCF-G	Waste concrete fines – gutter
XRD	X-ray diffraction

1. INTRODUCTION

With the adoption of the Paris Climate Agreement in 2015 (Fahimizadeh et al., 2020; Stern & Valero, 2021) and the Green Deal for Europe in 2019, global society has committed to reducing greenhouse gas and carbon dioxide emissions (Kludze et al., 2022; Stern & Valero, 2021). The overproduction of CO₂, a primary driver of global warming, plays a major role in the greenhouse effect (Ebi et al., 2021; Pandey & Kumar, 2014).

In this context, the construction sector emerges as a significant contributor to greenhouse gas emissions (Pandey & Kumar, 2019), accounting for roughly 7% of global CO₂ emissions (Fahimizadeh et al., 2020). Portland cement production, an essential binding component of most construction materials (Mohamad et al., 2022; Nodehi et al., 2022), accounts for 80% of these emissions (Adesina, 2020; Dapurkar & Telang, 2017; Z. Li et al., 2022b), mainly due to extraction of natural resources (Mohamad et al., 2022), and high energy consumption (Huntzinger & Eatmon, 2009). Other environmental impacts include noise pollution, the production of wastewater (Dunuweera & Rajapakse, 2018), vegetation degradation, soil erosion, or biodiversity loss (Mohamad et al., 2022).

The efforts to reuse and recycle are also driven by legislation measures addressing the huge amount of waste generation, with the majority of it (45-65%) landfilled (Lima et al., 2021). The current recycling methods for waste

65 concrete handling involves crushing the material with subsequent separation of fractions (Ding et al., 2022),
66 yielding coarse and fine aggregates and fine powder (C. Sun et al., 2020). Coarse aggregates with a diameter
67 greater than 4.75 mm (Luo et al., 2022) have a high potential for use in new concrete, road bases, or surface
68 material, among other applications (Ding et al., 2022; Nežerka et al., 2023a; C. Sun et al., 2020; Vanderzee &
69 Zeman, 2018). However, recycled aggregates can have issues with workability, lower strength or durability, which
70 can be resolved through consistent purification or carbonization processes (Prošek et al., 2020; C. Sun et al., 2020).

71 Waste concrete fines (WCF) particles with a diameter of less than 4.75 mm (Luo et al., 2022) account for up to
72 15-50 % of the volume of all crushed concrete, but their use is often regulated and restricted by legislation
73 (Evangelista et al., 2015; Nežerka et al., 2023a; Prošek et al., 2020). WCF has great potential for reuse, but storage
74 and long-term preservation are challenges that often lead to landfilling of the material (Ding et al., 2022; H.-F. Li
75 et al., 2022a). The effectiveness of using WCF in concrete largely depends on their particle size, which is typically
76 in the micrometre range. However, smaller particle sizes are associated with lower density and higher water
77 absorption (Rodrigues et al., 2013), which can negatively impact the long-term durability and strength of concrete
78 (Xiao et al., 2018), and are significantly affected by contaminants due to the recycling process (Evangelista et al.,
79 2015). Despite these drawbacks, small particle sizes offer residual reactivity, as investigated by Pawluczuk (2017)
80 and Xiao et al. (2018). In a prior review (Nežerka et al., 2023), we theorized the potential application of
81 a biomineralization process, specifically microbially induced calcite precipitation (MICP), for cementing WCF.
82 This approach has promise as a viable strategy to not only reduce the carbon footprint, but also embody the
83 principles of a circular economy.

84 MICP is a natural biomineralization process that uses microorganisms capable of biologically synthesizing
85 minerals via precipitation (Castro-Alonso et al., 2019; Qabany et al., 2012). During MICP, microorganisms
86 throughout different metabolic processes such as urea hydrolysis, oxidation of organic acids, amino acid
87 ammonification, or photosynthesis (Castanier et al., 1999), and specific enzymes, for example, urease (for the
88 hydrolysis of urea to form ammonia) (Castro-Alonso et al., 2019) or carbonic anhydrase, convert a supplied
89 substrate (chemical component) into precipitated minerals such as calcium carbonate (Dapurkar & Telang, 2017).
90 Most studies (Ghosh et al., 2019; Leeprasert et al., 2022; Nasser et al., 2022; Naveed et al., 2020; Torres-Aravena
91 et al., 2018) have verified that urea hydrolysis stands out as the most efficient process in terms of easiness
92 of process control, high substrate solubility and, importantly, rapid precipitation effectiveness. The precipitated
93 calcite can act as a binder on surfaces, and this feature can be utilised in various applications, e.g., for crack healing
94 and pore plugging for self-healing concrete (Abdel Gawwad et al., 2016; Intarasoontron et al., 2021; Pungrasmi

95 et al., 2019; X. Sun et al., 2019b; X. Sun et al., 2021b), for the production of sandstone bricks (X. Sun et al., 2021a)
1 or other different types of concrete materials (Intarasoontron et al., 2021; Skevi et al., 2021; Zhao et al., 2021a;
2 Zhao et al., 2021b), for soil improvements such as erosion control (X. Sun et al., 2022), soil consolidation and
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102 This study examined various conditions to optimize the biocementation process for binding WCF particles to form
103 compact composite samples. Biocementation using MICP has been conducted on various materials such as, e.g.
104 coarse aggregates (Mahawish et al., 2018; Nagy et al., 2023; Y. Sun et al., 2024), sands (Liufu et al., 2023; B.
105 Wang et al., 2024; Zeitouny et al., 2023) or soil (Bibi et al., 2018; Ji et al., 2024; Mujah et al., 2017), but there has
106 been no description of the recycling of WCF, focusing on the various factors that affect the compactness and
107 strength of the samples. The biocementation process in this study was achieved using the alkaliphilic bacterium
108 *Sporosarcina pasteurii* DSM 33 (with proven ureolytic activity), which facilitated the precipitation of calcium
109 carbonate crystals in the presence of urea and calcium ions. We hypothesized that adding essential nutrients and
110 substances will enable the *S. pasteurii* DSM 33 precipitation of calcite, consequently strengthening the WCF, and
111 that the physicochemical properties of WCF could affect the final properties of the formed composite samples.

36 112 **2. MATERIALS AND METHODS**

37 113 *2.1. WCF*

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39 114 For our study, WCF were obtained by grinding concrete of different types and ages. The first WCF material, WCF-
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121 The second WCF material, WCF-H, was prepared by grinding stripped concrete from the Czech D1 highway,
122 which connects the cities of Prague and Brno, during its reconstruction. It was made from a 60-year-old concrete
123 obtained by crushing and grinding the structural layers of the modernised D1 highway section between Loket and
124 Hořice (km 66.32–75.92). The concrete used in the highway construction was classified according to the EN 260-

1 standard, with strength grades ranging from C16/20 to C25/30, indicating compressive strengths between 16 to 25 MPa at 28 days. During the processing of WCF from the highway concrete (WCF-H), particles exceeding 10 mm were excluded. The remaining material was crushed using a hammer crusher and then finely ground to a fraction <1 mm using a Lavaris SKD 600 high-speed electric mill (230 kW).

As a result of the different grinding processes and aggregate composition within the recycled concrete samples, the particle size distribution of WCF materials was different. WCF-G samples contained smaller particles (mean diameter 5.08 μm), while the distribution of WCF-H was shifted towards larger fractions (mean diameter 7.33 μm). The particle size distribution curves are provided in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Cumulative particle-size distribution for the studied WCF materials determined using Fritsch Analyssete 22 Micro Tec Plus laser diffraction particle size analyzer.

2.2. Bacterial strain, culture media and growth conditions

This study utilized the gram-positive, alkaliphilic bacterium *Sporosarcina pasteurii* DSM 33 (ATCC 11859), which exhibits ureolytic activity and was obtained from the German Collection of Microorganisms and Cell Cultures GmbH (DSMZ, Braunschweig) (Ghosh et al., 2019). *S. pasteurii* DSM 33 was cultivated in Tryptone Soya Broth (TSB, Oxoid) medium with the pH adjusted to 7.3 ± 0.2 and sterilised by autoclaving at 121 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 15 minutes and supplemented with urea at a final concentration of 20 g/L. The cultivation was performed at 28 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ with shaking at 120 rpm for 48 hours. The strain was stored at 4 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ on Tryptone Soya Agar (TSA, Oxoid) with the addition of urea (20 g/L) and was routinely subcultured at fresh medium every 2–3 weeks to maintain its viability. To induce the precipitation of calcite crystals and binding of WCF particles, a biocementation solution consisting of Nutrient Broth (NB, Oxoid) medium (4 g/L, pH adjusted to 6.8 ± 0.2), urea (20 g/L) and CaCl_2

(2.8 g/L) was used. The stock solutions of urea (160 g/L) and CaCl₂ (28 g/L) were always sterilised by filtering through PTFE filters (0.2 µm pore size, Sigma-Aldrich) and added into media after autoclaving.

2.3. Ureolytic activity assay

Ureolytic activity was determined using the phenol-hypochlorite method described by G. Kim and Youn (2016). Briefly, *S. pasteurii* DSM 33 was grown in TSB supplemented with urea (20 g/L). The bacterial culture was centrifuged (6 000g, 4 °C for 10 minutes), and the pellets were washed twice with 50 mM 4-(2-hydroxyethyl)piperazine-1-ethanesulfonic acid (HEPES) buffer. The cells were sonicated on ice (three pulses of 30 seconds each), and centrifuged (6 000g, 4 °C for 10 minutes). The obtained supernatant (0.5 ml) was mixed with 0.5 ml of urease buffer (50 mM HEPES, 25 mM urea), and the resulting volume of 1 ml was incubated at 37 °C for 20 minutes. To stop the reaction, aliquots were transferred to 15 ml centrifuge tubes containing 1.5 ml of solution A (10 g/L phenol and 50 mg/L sodium nitroprusside, acting as a catalyst) and 1.5 ml of solution B (5 mg/ml NaOH and 0.044 % v/v NaClO). The mixture was stirred and incubated at 37 °C for 30 minutes, and the absorbance was measured at a wavelength of 620 nm. Ureolytic activity was quantified in triplicate during the growth curve at time points of 0, 24, 38, 48, 65, 72 and 90 hours. To construct a standard curve, ammonium chloride solution was utilised, as outlined in the protocol from the Urease Activity Assay Kit (ab204697, Abcam Trading Co., China): 0, 4, 12, 20, 32, 64 and 128 nmol/100 µl. Each concentration was transferred to a 96-well microtiter plate in 8 replicates, and the absorbance was measured using a spectrophotometer at a wavelength of 620 nm.

2.4 Biocementation - experimental design

S. pasteurii DSM 33 was grown in TSB supplemented with urea (20 g/L) at 28 °C, 120 rpm. After 48 hours, cells were centrifuged at 10 000g for 10 minutes at 4 °C, then washed and resuspended in a saline solution containing 9 g/L NaCl. The optical density at 600 nm (OD₆₀₀) was adjusted by diluting the centrifuged suspension to 2.5 or 5.0 and further used for the MICP process. In stage 1, we adopted parameters from the literature, further discussed in the Results section, primarily to familiarize ourselves with MICP processes and to preliminarily confirm their applicability to WCF as opposed to soils or sands; rigorous testing and validation were reserved for stage 2, where we focused our main efforts to investigate the impact of WCF composition and MICP treatment duration.

2.4.1 Optimization of MICP treatment (stage 1)

WCF suspensions for biocementation were prepared by mixing 7 g of WCF-G with 10 ml of sterile saline solution (9 g/L NaCl). During stage 1, we optimized preliminary parameters impacting sample compactness and integrity, as follows: (i) *S. pasteurii* DSM 33 bacterial cell concentration (OD₆₀₀ values of 2.5 and 5.0), (ii) pH adjustment of the WCF suspension from an initial pH of 12.1–12.3 to 6.8±0.2 using 1M HCl, and (iii) single or repeated

177 applications of bacterial suspension (Table S1). Each variant was prepared in triplicate. For all samples, 10 ml of
 178 bacterial suspension was mixed with the WCF suspension and transferred to containers. After settling for 24 hours,
 179 10 ml of biocementation solution was added at 48-hour intervals, alternating with the bacterial suspension
 180 in samples designated for repeated addition of bacterial suspension. Sterile (control) samples, which did not
 181 undergo MICP treatment, were prepared by mixing 7 g of sterile WCF-G (sterilized at 280 °C for 2 hours) with
 182 saline solution added at corresponding time points instead of the biocementation solution. The temperature for
 183 MICP treatment was set up to 28 °C, which is optimal cultivation temperature for *S. pasteurii* DSM 33 (Onal
 184 Okyay & Frigi Rodrigues, 2014). After five additions of biocementation solution, all samples were dried,
 185 the compactness of the composite samples were analyzed.

Table S1: Summary of prepared and tested specimens in stage 1.

Samples	DSM 33	DSM 33	pH adjusted to	MICP solution ^a
	OD ₆₀₀ =5 [ml]	OD ₆₀₀ =2.5 [ml]	6.8 ± 0.2 (1M HCl) [ml]	[ml]
WCF-G-01	10+10 ^b	-	-	10
WCF-G-02	-	10+10 ^b	-	10
WCF-G-03	10	-	2	10
WCF-G-04	10+10 ^b	-	2	10
WCF-G-05	-	10+10 ^b	2	10

^a solutions were added consistently every 48 to 72 hours

^b repeated addition of bacterial suspension

The compactness of the biocemented WCF-G was recorded based on i) the percentage of the largest associated material (>15 mm) and consolidated grains of material (10-15 mm), and ii) the frequency and thickness of cracks in biocemented conglomerates.

The samples were classified based on their compactness into three categories (Figure 2):

- 1) Non-cemented: These samples had a powdery structure with no apparent cementation.
- 2) Disintegrated upon removal: These samples did not maintain structural integrity when taken out of the containers.
- 3) Stiff conglomerates: These stiff samples sustained handling.

Figure 2: Illustration of sample compactness categories: non-cemented sample (right), partially cemented sample (middle), and fully cemented sample (left).

Based on this classification, the parameters of the MICP treatment that showed the best compactness of the samples, were selected for further experiments in stage 2.

2.4.2 Effect of treatment duration (stage 2)

In stage 2, we further investigated the effects of MICP treatment duration together with impact of WCF properties (composition and particle mean size) on the strength and compactness of the resulting conglomerates. Therefore, within the stage 2, additional WCF material of differing origin and grading (WCF-H, as detailed in Section 2.1) was used.

In stage 2, samples were prepared similarly to stage 1, with 7 g of WCF in 10 ml of saline solution, adjusting the pH to 6.8 ± 0.2 and using an *S. pasteurii* DSM 33 concentration of $OD_{600} 5.0$. Biocementation was carried out over various durations (14, 30, 60, and 90 days) to determine the optimal treatment period. The biocementation and saline solutions were added consistently every 48–72 hours, with six replicates per sample (including sterile samples) (see Table S2). At the end of each treatment period, biocemented WCF samples were dried at 28 °C for 30 days before further analyses (SEM, XRD, and EDS). Compactness was evaluated visually, as described in stage 1, and strength of compact samples underwent macroscopic indentation testing (Figure 3).

Table S2: Summary of prepared and tested specimens in stage 2.

Samples	MICP treatment	DSM 33 OD ₆₀₀ =5 [ml]	Saline ^b [ml]	MICP
				(biocementation) solution ^c [ml]
WCF-G14	14 days	10	-	10
WCF-G30	30 days	10	-	10
WCF-G60	60 days	10	-	10

WCF-G90	90 days	10	-	10
WCF-H14	14 days	10	-	10
WCF-H30	30 days	10	-	10
WCF-H60	60 days	10	-	10
WCF-H90	90 days	10	-	10
WCF-S-G90 ^a	90 days	-	10	-
WCF-S-H90 ^a	90 days	-	10	-

^a sterile samples

^{b, c} solutions were added consistently every 48 to 72 hours.

The macroscopic indentation (details and images provided in Holeček et al. (2023)) was conducted on selected samples using a displacement-controlled loading rate of 0.5 mm/min. The steel indenter was conically shaped, featuring a tip width of 0.15 mm, a base width of 12.2 mm, and a tip angle of 60°. The loading procedure was carried out with an MTS Criterion Series 40 loading frame.

Figure 3: Indentation of hardened samples using a conically-shaped steel indenter

2.5. Scanning electron microscope: microscopy imaging

The calcium carbonate structures formed by bacteria or spontaneous carbonation were observed using a ZEISS FEG Merlin Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM) for microstructural and elemental analysis, equipped with a Schottky cathode (10 kV accelerating voltage, 1 nA current, 8.5 mm working distance, 50 μ s dwell time per point, and 1024 px resolution). The vacuum required for SEM and sample preparation procedures kills bacteria, making it impossible to study their viability and the CaCO₃ formation process.

Secondary electron (SE) detectors enabled the observation of the topology of the surfaces under investigation, while backscattered electron (BSE) detectors were employed to determine the distribution of phases in the samples based on the atomic numbers of their constituent elements. Elemental microanalysis was performed using an Oxford Instruments X-ray energy-dispersive spectrometer (EDS) to determine the mass and atomic percentages of chemical elements, both in point analysis and 2D fields. Phases were identified from their elemental compositions using stoichiometry.

Samples for SEM analysis were prepared in two forms:

1. The samples were cut using a Struers Secotom 50 precision cutting machine to determine the distribution of individual phases and elements. Due to the brittle structure of the samples and to prevent disintegration and removal of CaCO₃ during sample preparation, the samples were impregnated with Stuers EpoFix epoxy resin, which was subsequently pressed into the sample microstructure using a vacuum pump. Each batch and bacterial exposure time were represented by one sample. The prepared sample was then polished using SiC abrasive foils (grain size 1000-4000 grains/cm²). The sample was subsequently coated in an argon atmosphere with a 3 nm platinum layer to increase conductivity, which is essential for SEM and EDS analysis.
2. To determine the shape, size, and quantity of crystals, samples of the solidified material were ground again and placed on an adhesive target. These samples were also coated with a 6 nm thick platinum layer in an argon atmosphere due to the increased number of irregularities on the sample.

2.6. X-ray diffraction

Powder X-ray diffraction (XRD) was utilised to identify and assess individual phases of crystalline origin by recording the intensity of diffracted radiation when exposed to monochromatic X-ray radiation with gradually varying diffraction angles (Stanjek & Häusler, 2004). An Aeris XRD analyser by Malvern Panalytical was used, with the parameters set to $2\theta^\circ = 5-85$. The analyser was equipped with a cobalt anode and a K α filter. The Rietveld method, specifically the software Profex, was used to evaluate the results (Doebelin & Kleeberg, 2015). The amorphous phase was quantified using an internal standard, with 20% ZnO added to the sample.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Factors affecting the MICP process and compactness of the samples (stage 1 testing)

Bacterial biomineralization plays a fundamental role in biogeochemical cycles, and has significant technological and environmental applications that are greatly influenced by various factors and conditions (González-Muñoz et al., 2010). In our study, various factors such as pH adjustment, bacterial cell concentration and single or repeated addition of bacteria were tested on the success of the MICP treatment of WCF-G.

To ensure the highest ureolytic activity of *S. pasteurii* DSM 33 during the bacteria addition to WCF-G, the growth curve together with ureolytic activity was measured. The exponential phase was observed between 24-48 hours of cultivation, followed by the entry of cells into the stationary phase (Figure 4). Ureolytic activity was assessed concurrently with the growth curve using a phenol-hypochlorite ureolytic assay at six-time intervals. We found that the peak ureolytic activity occurred between 36 and 48 hours, which corresponds to the late exponential phase. These results are consistent with previous studies (Babakhani et al., 2021; Fang et al., 2021; 2019; Omoregie et al., 2020; X. Sun et al., 2019a) and provide valuable insights for optimizing ureolytic activity in biocementation applications.

Figure 4: Growth curve of *Sporosarcina pasteurii* DSM 33

When examining the concentrations of bacterial cells (OD₆₀₀ 2.5 and OD₆₀₀ 5.0) with either single or repeated addition and the pH adjustment of WCF-G suspensions in stage 1, the concentration of bacterial cells turned out to be the crucial parameter for successful MICP. Similarly, Erdmann et al. (2022) determined the optimal bacterial concentration with OD₆₀₀ of 1.6 for MICP of sandy waste materials. Interestingly, some studies using sand particles applied a significantly lower initial bacterial cell concentration, with an OD₆₀₀ of 0.8-1.2 (Al Qabany et al., 2012;

287 L. Chen et al., 2022). We chose the cell concentration for our experiment based on the studies of J. Zhang et al.
288 (2021), H.-J. Chen et al. (2019) and Abdel Gawwad et al. (2016), which showed that a bacterial culture with an
289 OD_{600} of 2.4-2.5 resulted in greater calcite precipitation compared to samples with lower cell concentrations (OD_{600}
290 of 0.5-1.0). In our experiment, all samples exhibited more compact WCF-G grains when the higher bacterial cell
291 suspension (OD_{600} 5.0) was applied. In these samples, a total of $68.0\pm 3.2\%$ of the WCF-G particles aggregated in
292 fractions larger than 15 mm and between 10-15 mm; in comparison, when a lower concentration of bacterial cells
293 (OD_{600} 2.5) was used, the proportion of these aggregated WCF-G-consolidated grains was only $48.0\pm 7.6\%$.
294 In addition, the compactness was found to be more pronounced in samples in which the initial pH of the suspension
295 was adjusted to 6.8 ± 0.2 . Typically, during calcite precipitation the pH increases, and once it exceeds 10.0, the
296 ureolytic activity decreases (Torres-Aravena et al., 2018). Therefore, WCF's initial strongly alkaline environment
297 (pH 11-12) did not provide optimal conditions for MICP. This is in agreement with the studies of J. Zhang et al.
298 (2021), Fu et al. (2022), Ghosh et al. (2019) and Gunjo Kim et al. (2018), who adjusted the pH to 6.5 ± 0.2 . In
299 contrast, Qiu et al. (2014) tested MICP with recycled concrete aggregate (RCA) with original pH 9.0-10.0 adjusted
300 to 8.2, which is optimal for the growth of *S. pasteurii*. However, in this case a lower cell concentration ($\sim 10^6$
301 cells/ml) was used to prevent a rapid increase in pH, which would halt calcite precipitation. Therefore, in our
302 experiments, we adjusted the pH of the WCF-G suspension to 6.8 ± 0.2 to ensure $CaCO_3$ precipitation. In this
303 scenario, the medium flowing out from the containers had a pH between 9.5 and 11, indicating that the
304 biocementation process had taken place.
305 When assessing the effects of the single or repeated addition of *S. pasteurii* DMS 33 (OD_{600} concentration of 5.0)
306 at a consistent pH of the initial WCF-G suspension (6.8 ± 0.2), the consolidated WCF-G formed a compact structure
307 that accounted for 61 to 87% of the entire sample. However, significant discrepancies were found in the presence
308 of cracks and discontinuities within the samples. Based on the results (**Error! Reference source not found.**), most
309 of the WCF-G samples did not form compact conglomerates. However, WCF-G samples with only single addition
310 of bacterial suspension with $OD_{600} = 5$ and with pH adjustment produced stiff conglomerate with high stiffness.
311 Other composites (with different tested parameters) resulted in poorly cemented conglomerates that disintegrated
312 upon removal from the containers.

Based on these findings, in the subsequent experiment (stage 2), which tested the optimal duration of the MICP process, the following parameters were selected: adjustment of the initial pH of the WCF-G suspension to 6.8 ± 0.2 , and the single addition of *S. pasteurii* DSM 33 ($OD_{600} 5.0$).

Table S3: Classification of samples based on their compactness.

Samples	1	2	3
WCF-G-01	Medium	Medium	Poor
WCF-G-02	Poor	Poor	Poor
WCF-G-03	Medium	Poor	High
WCF-G-04	Poor	Poor	Poor
WCF-G-05	Poor	Poor	Poor

3.2 Effect of MICP duration (stage 2 testing)

The tested experimental conditions were further verified on two types of WCFs (highway (WCF-H) and gutter (WCF-G)) differing in their physicochemical properties, and the objective was to analyse the effect of the length of biocementation (14, 30, 60 and 90 days) on the properties of the resulting composite materials. The formed composites, with six replicates for each variant, were characterized by the amount of $CaCO_3$, mechanical properties and visual appearance, as shown in Figure 5. Additionally, a more comprehensive analyses of the samples were performed using additional measurements, including SEM, EDS, and XRD.

Figure 5: The WCF-H sample subjected to the biocementation process at stage 2: original sample (A), after 14 days (B), after 30 days (C), after 65 days (D), after 90 days of MICP (E), final compact composite of WCF-H after 90 days of MICP (F), control (sterile) sample (G).

3.2.1. SEM analyses of specimens (stage 2 testing)

The $CaCO_3$ crystals in the cemented WCF-G samples appeared as very fine formations, forming clusters and elongated columnar crystals. The crushed grains of the original concrete (including both aggregate and cement matrix) were sharp-edged and irregular.

335 Figure 6 (A) shows the formation of CaCO_3 of bacterial origin in clusters, ranging from small formations of up to
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2 336 100 nm to elongated columnar crystals of 1.5 μm . In the sterile control samples, no such formations were observed.
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4 337 Recent research (Gu et al., 2022) reported that CaCO_3 formations begin after 24 hours and become more distinct
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6 338 after 48 hours, and with repeated addition of the biocementation solution, the crystals continue to transform and
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8 339 form. For this reason, we also tested the factor of the duration of adding the biocementation solution and its effect
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10 340 on the morphology and size of the crystals. Finally, adding the biocementation solution for 14 days was insufficient
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12 341 to form CaCO_3 crystals. Conversely, the duration of the addition of the biocementing solution (30, 60 and 90 days)
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14 342 had no effect on the structure, shape, or type of the crystals formed.
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16 343 CaCO_3 in the WCF-H sample occurred as small formations in crushed concrete (due to carbonation), as tiny flakes
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18 344 or scales (formed during solution application or sample crushing) (Gu et al., 2022; Qian et al., 2021), or as clusters
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20 345 of irregular formations (resulting from bacterial activity) (Bayati & Saadabadi, 2021). The aggregate had sharp
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22 346 edges and parallel texture, while the cement matrix was both amorphous and sharp. The original concrete's sharp-
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24 347 edged structure was acquired during the recycling process of crushing into fine powder.
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26 348 Figure 6 (B) shows bacterial-origin CaCO_3 cluster formations ranging in size from several nanometers to one
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28 349 micrometre. On the other hand, sterile samples did not contain similar CaCO_3 clusters or were only rarely visible
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30 350 and at very low concentrations. The analysis of sterile gutter and highway samples revealed leaf- or flake-like
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32 351 formations throughout (Figure 6 C, D) due to the crystallisation of substances from the physiological solution. The
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34 352 chemical composition of these areas confirmed that they consist of CaCO_3 .

353 Figure 6: SEM images of CaCO_3 crystals detected in MICP-cemented samples WCF-G (A) and WCF-H (B), and
 354 clusters of WCF grains covered with flaky CaCO_3 crystals in sterile samples, WCF-G (C) and WCF-H (D). The
 355 images (A)-(D) were taken at magnifications of 15k \times , 15k \times , 5k \times , and 10k \times , respectively.

356 3.3.2. BSE-EDS measurements (stage 2 testing)

357 The presence of CaCO_3 in the samples was verified by EDS analysis. The studied formations of the bacterial
 358 samples contained the elements carbon (C), calcium (Ca), and oxygen (O) in a certain ratio. From the ratio of these
 359 elements, it was concluded that they could be attributed to CaCO_3 (Ghosh et al., 2019). Detailed information about
 360 the microstructure of the sample and the precipitated CaCO_3 was obtained by SEM BSE microscopy. Figures 7A
 361 and B show SEM images of the samples prepared by method 1, as described in Section 2.5. A thin section for each
 362 sample was impregnated with epoxy resin and polished perfectly to form a flat surface, allowing EDS measurement
 363 to identify and quantify different phases. The SEM images are complemented by map spectra showing each
 364 element's distribution. For better visualization, only the most represented elements have been highlighted in
 365 colour: carbon in red, calcium in yellow, silicon in dark blue, and oxygen in light blue (O).

368 Figure 7: BSE images under 5kx magnification of the microstructure of sterile WCF-S-H90 (A) and biocemented
 369 WCF-H90 samples (B), complemented by colour-coded map spectra of the different elements. Comparison of
 370 EDS spectra from the whole area of both images (C).

371 Figure 7A shows the microstructure of the sterile sample WCF-S-H90, demonstrating the high presence
 372 of siliceous aggregate (blue parts) and areas of cementitious matrix. The space between the grains was filled with
 373 carbon, representing the epoxy resin that filled the empty pores during sample preparation. Figure 7B shows the
 374 WCF-H90 sample treated with bacteria. This sample also contained silica aggregate and cementitious matrix. The
 375 voids and pores between the grains were largely filled with calcium carbonate (yellow-red areas). These CaCO_3
 376 formations were also observed in other studies (Feng et al., 2021; Lin et al., 2020; Tang et al., 2023; Tobler et al.,
 377 2018), even in a similar study to ours, dealing with sand biocementation (Iamchaturapatr et al., 2021). The
 378 biocemented samples contained mostly CaCO_3 clusters with very few single crystals (Z. Wang et al., 2022b).
 379 Other elements (iron, aluminium, sodium, magnesium, and sulphur) were not present in significant amounts,
 380 as documented by the energy spectrum generated from the whole area in Figure 7C, comparing the spectra from

381 the full image area. The energy spectrum of the sterile sample from the whole of Figure 7A is shown in yellow,
382 and the energy spectrum of the biocemented sample from the whole of Figure 7B is shown in red.
383 EDS analysis of the sterile samples showed significantly lower concentrations of CaCO_3 , while the elements in
384 the aggregate and cement matrix (Si, Fe, Al) were present in higher concentrations than in the MICP-treated
385 samples. The trace amount of sulphur can be attributed to the origin of the WCF material and the presence
386 of gypsum.

3.2.3. XRD analysis: CaCO_3 content (stage 2 testing)

387 CaCO_3 may naturally occur in samples as aggregate, through carbonation, or as a result of bacterial activity (Bayati
388 & Saadabadi, 2021). The morphology of CaCO_3 is divided, in addition to a rare amorphous structure (Scrivener et
389 al., 2015), into three forms: calcite (the most stable form, which can form a wide variety of crystal shapes),
390 aragonite (elongated, columnar crystals), and vaterite (the least stable form, characterised by oval formations)
391 (Dhami et al., 2013; Ghosh et al., 2019; Omoregie et al., 2019; Šovljanski et al., 2021). The crystal form is
392 influenced by many factors, such as the source of calcium, the kinetics of the precipitation process, the composition
393 of the biocement solution, etc. (Murugan et al., 2021). Previous studies (Heveran et al., 2019; Mitchell & Ferris,
394 2006; Xu et al., 2020) described a transition from the less stable vaterite and aragonite phases to the more stable
395 calcite phase during CaCO_3 precipitation. Consistent with this trend, our findings demonstrate that calcite was the
396 predominant form present in all biocemented samples (Figure 8). As the MICP treatment progressed, the vaterite
397 concentration decreased while the concentrations of the more stable aragonite and calcite crystals increased,
398 as documented in Figure 6, for both WCF-G and WCF-H samples. Furthermore, the untreated WCF samples and
399 the sterile samples treated at 90 days exhibited similarly lower calcite concentrations.

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Figure 8: XRD diffractograms illustrating the shift from vaterite to more stable aragonite and predominant calcite forms over time in WCF-G and WCF-H samples. The comparison against untreated/sterile samples at 90 days (WCF-S-G90a and WCF-S-H90a) highlights increased calcite concentrations in treated samples within stage 2.

For a clearer representation of individual CaCO₃ phases, see Figure 9.

Figure 9: Concentration of CaCO₃ crystals for different types of WCF materials and different treatments of the studied stage 2 samples based on XRD results.

As for aggregate content, both sample types (WCF-G and WCF-H) contained similar minerals. The highway-derived samples revealed an aggregate composed of quartz, feldspar, and mica, as well as a probable presence of calcite (which appears in greater amounts than can be attributed solely to concrete carbonation). In the gutter-derived sample, a smaller amount of quartz and a reduced concentration of calcite were observed. Other studies that investigated WCF (Liu et al., 2022) and other alkaline materials, for example, alkali-activated slag mortar (Bayati & Saadabadi, 2021; Çelikten et al., 2019; Türker et al., 2016), found that the aggregates contained similar proportions of quartz and feldspar, among other similarities. In all cases, the presence of quartz and feldspar

423 is assumed to positively affect the precipitation of CaCO₃ crystals and the effective filling of pores and microcracks
1
2 424 in highly alkaline materials. Subsequent studies were focused on the impact of the size of WCF on final porosity
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4 425 in composite samples and their mechanical stiffness (Holeček et al., 2023).
5

6 426 *3.3. Evaluation of compactness and strength for samples within stage 2*

7 427 Given that the indentation method exceeds the microstructural scale, the indentation curves obtained reflect the
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9 428 bulk mechanical behavior of the material. For the conglomerates, elastic stiffness (k) was assessed as the tangent
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11 429 to the linear portion of the load-displacement ($F(u)-u$) curves (Figures 10 and 11). Consistency was maintained by
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13 430 defining the linear interval for stiffness calculation as a uniform 0.4 mm displacement leading up to the peak load.
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15 431 This standardization ensures direct comparability of stiffness values across different samples.
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18 432 This study hypothesizes that material stiffness is indicative of the strength of chemical bonds within the WCF
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20 433 conglomerates, given that these bonds influence the bulk mechanical properties of the material.
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Figure 10: Load-displacement diagrams obtained during the indentation tests for the WCF-H samples.

Figure 11: Load-displacement diagrams obtained during the indentation tests for the WCF-G samples.

Most of the sterile WCF-G samples, or those subjected to MICP for a short duration (14 days), did not form compact conglomerates. This lack of compactness correlates with a low calcite concentration, as identified by XRD analysis (Table S4). Samples of WCF-G that underwent extended treatment and both sterile and MICP-treated WCF-H samples exposed to short treatment (14 days) generally resulted in poorly cemented conglomerates that disintegrated upon removal from the containers. However, longer treatment periods (30 to 90 days) for WCF-H samples produced compact conglomerates with significantly enhanced stiffness.

448 Table S4: Classification of samples based on their compactness.

Samples	1	2	3	4	5	6
WCF-S-G90	Poor	Poor	Poor	Poor	Poor	Poor
WCF-G14	Poor	Poor	Poor	Medium	Poor	Poor
WCF-G30	Poor	Poor	Medium	Medium	Medium	Medium
WCF-G60	Medium	Medium	Medium	Poor	Poor	Medium
WCF-G90	Medium	Medium	Poor	Poor	Medium	Medium
WCF-S-H90	Medium	Medium	Medium	Medium	Medium	Medium
WCF-H14	High	High	High	Medium	Medium	Medium
WCF-H30	High	High	High	Medium	Medium	High
WCF-H60	High	Medium	High	High	High	High
WCF-H90	Medium	High	High	High	High	High

449
 450 Interestingly, the sterile WCF-S-H90 and MICP-treated WCF-G30 samples that were sufficiently compact for
 451 indentation demonstrated relatively high stiffness values (Figure 12). It is important to note, though, that the
 452 measured stiffness values showed considerable variability.

454
 455 Figure 12: Indentation stiffness k evaluated for WCF-H samples (left) and WCF-G samples (H).

4. CONCLUSION

456
 457 Our study unveils a novel avenue for recycling disintegrated construction waste materials, extending promising
 458 applications to a broader spectrum of bulk construction waste and creating new opportunities to reduce the carbon
 459 footprint and support circular economy goals. In stage 1, we conducted initial parameter testing (pH adjustment,
 460 cell concentration and single or repeated addition of bacterial suspension) based on literature values to confirm
 461 that MICP processes, typically applied to soils and sands, could also be effective for WCF. This allowed us to
 462 refine the MICP treatment parameters for stage 2, where we focused on systematically evaluating the impacts
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464 of treatment duration. Our results demonstrate that the MICP strategy using ureolytic bacteria is indeed a viable
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2 465 approach for recycling WCF, contributing to a more sustainable option for concrete waste reuse. Specifically, we
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4 466 observed that time, pH, and varying concentrations of bacterial suspension significantly influence the
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6 467 consolidation and aggregation of individual grains into compact WCF samples. The biocemented samples
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8 468 contained a variety of crystal sizes, with crystals as large as 5 μm identified through SEM analysis, while XRD
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10 469 confirmed the presence of aragonite and calcite as the primary CaCO_3 polymorphs formed during MICP, listed in
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12 470 ascending order of thermodynamic stability. Notably, the content of the less stable vaterite decreased slightly
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14 471 during MICP, transitioning into more stable forms in both types of WCF samples, originating from a prefabricated
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16 472 gutter and an old highway concrete layer. This suggests that the duration of MICP treatment influences CaCO_3
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18 473 polymorph distribution, as shown by the low concentrations of calcite and aragonite detected in untreated, sterile
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20 474 WCF samples. Mineral composition analysis of both types revealed similar aggregate contents; however, the
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22 475 highway-derived samples exhibited a higher calcite content with aggregates of quartz, feldspar, and mica, whereas
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24 476 the gutter-derived samples contained less quartz and a lower calcite concentration.

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26 477 To improve the sustainability of this recycling process, future studies should focus on assessing economic and
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28 478 environmental feasibility through life cycle assessment. Utilizing agricultural or food industry waste as alternative
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30 479 nutrient sources for bacterial growth or calcite precipitation could help lower costs and increase affordability, given
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32 480 the relatively high expenses of the current approach. Other limitation of this study lies in the strength and stiffness
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34 481 of the resulting samples. Future research should thus conduct an in-depth evaluation of the mechanical properties
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36 482 of the composites, considering the physicochemical characteristics of the WCF. Another solution may be to use
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38 483 bacteria adapted to lower temperatures, which would also reduce the cost of the technology. Additionally,
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40 484 exploring strategies like reinforcing WCF materials with natural fibers or applying compression could enhance the
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42 485 performance and viability of this method. Ultimately, our research contributes to the growing body of knowledge
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44 486 on sustainable construction materials and highlights the potential of MICP as a viable approach to recycling
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46 487 construction waste.

488 **DATA AVAILABILITY**

489 The datasets used and/or analyzed during the current study are available from the corresponding author on request.
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797 **Ethical Approval**

798 All authors and co-authors agree with the Ethical Responsibilities of Authors in ESPR. The journal may use
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801 **Consent to participate**

802 All authors and co-authors agree with the participation and authorship of this article “Application of *Sporosarcina*
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2 803 *pasteurii* for the biomineralisation of calcite in the treatment of waste concrete fines”.

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7 805 **Consent to publish**

8 806 All authors and co-authors agree with the submission and publication in this journal.

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12 808 **Authors Contributions**

13 809 All authors contributed to the study conception and design. Material preparation, data collection and analysis were
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Table S1: Summary of prepared and tested specimens in stage 1.

Samples	DSM 33	DSM 33	pH adjusted to	MICP solution ^a
	OD ₆₀₀ =5 [ml]	OD ₆₀₀ =2.5 [ml]	6.8 ± 0.2 (1M HCl) [ml]	[ml]
WCF-G-01	10+10 ^b	-	-	10
WCF-G-02	-	10+10 ^b	-	10
WCF-G-03	10	-	2	10
WCF-G-04	10+10 ^b	-	2	10
WCF-G-05	-	10+10 ^b	2	10

^a solutions were added consistently every 48 to 72 hours

^b repeated addition of bacterial suspension

Table S2: Summary of prepared and tested specimens in stage 2.

Samples	MICP treatment	DSM 33	Saline ^b [ml]	MICP
		OD ₆₀₀ =5 [ml]		(biocementation) solution ^c [ml]
WCF-G14	14 days	10	-	10
WCF-G30	30 days	10	-	10
WCF-G60	60 days	10	-	10
WCF-G90	90 days	10	-	10
WCF-H14	14 days	10	-	10
WCF-H30	30 days	10	-	10
WCF-H60	60 days	10	-	10
WCF-H90	90 days	10	-	10
WCF-S-G90 ^a	90 days	-	10	-
WCF-S-H90 ^a	90 days	-	10	-

^a sterile samples

^{b, c} solutions were added consistently every 48 to 72 hours.

Table S3: Classification of samples based on their compactness.

Samples	1	2	3
WCF-G-01	Medium	Medium	Poor
WCF-G-02	Poor	Poor	Poor
WCF-G-03	Medium	Poor	High
WCF-G-04	Poor	Poor	Poor
WCF-G-05	Poor	Poor	Poor

Table S4: Classification of samples based on their compactness.

Samples	1	2	3	4	5	6
WCF-S-G90	Poor	Poor	Poor	Poor	Poor	Poor
WCF-G14	Poor	Poor	Poor	Medium	Poor	Poor
WCF-G30	Poor	Poor	Medium	Medium	Medium	Medium
WCF-G60	Medium	Medium	Medium	Poor	Poor	Medium
WCF-G90	Medium	Medium	Poor	Poor	Medium	Medium
WCF-S-H90	Medium	Medium	Medium	Medium	Medium	Medium
WCF-H14	High	High	High	Medium	Medium	Medium
WCF-H30	High	High	High	Medium	Medium	High
WCF-H60	High	Medium	High	High	High	High
WCF-H90	Medium	High	High	High	High	High

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